

ONE-POT TWO COMPONENT SYNTHESIS AND INVITRO STUDY OF BENZOXAZOLE PROMOTED BY CuI_2

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ABSTRACT

In this study, we present the design, synthesis, structural characterization, and biological evaluation of new benzoxazole from 2-aminophenol and substituted aldehydes in the presence of catalytic quantity of CuI_2 at room temperature. as possible therapeutic agents a two-component, one-pot cyclocondensation reaction using conventionally produced methods. Using mass spectrometry, ^1H NMR, and ^{13}C NMR, all substances were described. Furthermore, the desired compound outperformed the standard antibacterial activity by exhibiting notable against important bacterial strains, streptomycin and certain of its derivatives demonstrated moderate to high antibacterial effectiveness. These findings show that benzoxazole derivatives hold substantial promise for further development as medicinal agents.

KEYWORDS: Benzoxazole, One-pot two-component synthesis, 2-Aminophenol, Substituted aryl aldehydes, CuI_2 , Bioevaluation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Benzoxazole belongs to one of the most important class of heterocyclic compounds which are very significant for medicinal field. It has been incorporated in many medicinal compounds that made it versatile heterocyclic compound possessing wide spectrum of biological activities^[1-5], antimicrobial Antibacterial activity^[6], antimicrobial and anticancer agents.^[7,8] Keeping in view of the pharmacological importance of benzoxazole derivatives were

maintained. The present study had been synthesized some new benzoxazole derivatives and evaluate their antimicrobial and ant proliferative activities. The design of benzoxazole molecules with antimicrobial and anticancer potential was based on literature. The benzoxazole moiety is the key structure feature of a large number of biologically active natural products and pharmaceutical compounds. The synthesis of benzoxazole can be followed by various catalyst such Zirconium-catalyzed^[9], $\text{Co}_2(\text{CO})_8$ ^[10], Zinc triflates^[11], Pd/C^[12], $\text{Pb}(\text{OAc})_4$ ^[13], Nano- NiFe_2O_4 ^[14], $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4@ \text{SiO}_2\text{-SO}_3\text{H}$ Nanoparticle^[15], Nickel supported silica^[16], silico methods.^[17] Two protocols for the synthesis of benzoxazole have been developed. One is the nikelsulphate catalyzed intermolecular o-arylations or intermolecular domino annulations of 2-aminophenol and substituted aldehydes and the other is the direct condensation of 2-aminophenol with aldehyde under harsh conditions, such as in the presence of strong acid, high temperature⁵ or strong oxidants. Catalytic aerobic oxidation using oxygen as terminal oxidant has received much attention and been used in the synthesis of benzoxazoles. Nickel supported silica as an environmental friendly and economical catalyst has been attracting increasing research interest from chemists. Although kinds of NiSO_4 catalyzed organic transformations have been developed, the CuI_2 to form carbon-carbon and carbon-heteroatom bond has remained largely undeveloped. Herein, we report an efficient and environmentally friendly method for the synthesis of benzoxazole catalyzed by nickel supported silica at room temperature (Scheme-1).

We studied the possibility to synthesis of benzoxazole by the reaction of 2-aminophenol and substituted aldehyde employed CuI_2 as the catalyst (Scheme-1). Here, an efficient and simple procedure for the synthesis of desired derivatives is described and the synthesis of some compounds has been reported in our previous studies.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

All reagents and solvents were purchased and used without further purification. Crude products were purified by column chromatography on silica gel of 100–200 mesh. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded on the 400 MHz instruments, and spectral data are reported in ppm relative to tetramethylsilane (TMS) as internal standard. LCMS Mass spectra were recorded on a MASPEC low resolution mass spectrometer operating at 70 eV. To conclude, we have shown that the NiSO_4 is a highly active catalyst for the synthesis of benzoxazole.

2.1. GENERAL PROCEDURE FOR THE PREPARATION OF BENZOXAZOLE

A mixture of 2-aminophenol (1.mol) and substituted aromatic aldehydes (1mol) with CuI₂ (4mol%) in EtOH(30 mL) was stirred at ambient temperature for an appropriate time. After completion of the reaction as indicated by TLC, the CuI₂ was filtered and washed with absolute Alcohol. The crude product was purified by recrystallization from diethyl ether (solid products) or by chromatography using silica gel and mixtures of hexane/ethyl acetate of increasing polarity. The physical data was identified by ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and LCMS spectrometers.

2.1.1.2-Phenylbenzoxazole (3a)

Milky white solid, Yield-83%, M.P-174-176⁰C, ¹HNMR(400MHz,CDCl₃) δ ppm: 8.384–8.212(m, 2H,Ar–H), 7.747 (t, J = 7.2 Hz,1H,Ar–H), 7.625–7.424 (m, 4H, Ar–H),7.395–7.158 (m, 2H, Ar–H); ¹³CNMR(100 MHz,CDCl₃) δ ppm : 162.29, 151.57,142.40, 131.74, 128.58, 127.05, 127.41, 125.70, 124.55, 118.89, 110.65; LCMS(:m/z): 196.25 (M+1).Molecular formulae : C₁₃H₉NO.

2.1.3. 4-(benzo[d]oxazol-2-yl) phenol (3b)

Milky white solid, Yield-88%, M.P-178-180⁰C, ¹HNMR(400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ ppm: 9.157 (s,1H,-OH), 8.045 (d, J = 8.4 Hz, 2H, Ar–H), 7.710 (t, J = 7.8 Hz, 1H, Ar–H), 7.526 (t, J = 8.4 Hz, 1H,Ar–H), 7.384–7.295 (m, 4H, Ar–H), 2.012 (s, 3H, CH₃); ¹³CNMR(100 MHz,CDCl₃) δ ppm : δ 165.25, 151.06, 142.56, 142.84, 129.54, 127.40, 124.72, 124.82, 124.50,119.71, 110.68, 21.21; LCMS(:m/z): 212.44 (M+H); Molecular formulae: C₁₃H₉NO₂.

2.1.4.2-(4-Methoxyphenyl) benzoxazole (3c)

Milky white solid, Yield-90%, M.P-185-187⁰C, ¹HNMR(400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ ppm : 8.228 (d, J = 9.0 Hz, 2H, Ar–H), 7.844 (t, J = 7.9 Hz, 1H, Ar–H), 7.454(t, J = 8.0 Hz, 1H, Ar–H), 7.458–7.296 (m, 2H, Ar–H), 7.214 (d, J = 12.8 Hz, 2H,Ar–H), 3.725 (s, 3H, OCH₃); ¹³CNMR(100 MHz,CDCl₃) δ ppm: 163.92, 162.54,150.58, 142.24, 129.38, 126.47, 124.08, 119.58, 119.57, 114.71, 111.80, 55.20; LCMS(:m/z): 226 .78 (M+1). Molecular formulae: C₁₄H₁₁NO₂

2.1.6.2-(4-(Trifluoromethyl) phenyl) benzoxazole (3d)

Milky white solid, Yield-91%, M.P-191-193⁰C, ¹HNMR(400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ ppm : 8.458 (d, J = 8.0 Hz, 1H, Ar–H), 8.164 (d, J = 7.2 Hz, 1H, Ar–H), 7.654 (t, J = 7.6 Hz, 2H, Ar–H), 7.546–7.458 (m, 2H, Ar–H), 7.388–7.317 (m,2H, Ar–H); ¹³CNMR(100 MHz,CDCl₃) δ ppm : 164.08, 152.84, 140.88, 132.27,130.14, 129.47, 128.54, 127.38, 125.17, 124.09, 123.84,

120.34, 110.58; LCMS:(m/z): 263.56 (M+1). Molecular formulae: C₁₄H₈NO.

2.1.7.2-(4-(Chlorophyll) benzoxazole (3e)

Milky white solid, Yield-90%, M.P-186-188⁰C, ¹HNMR(400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ ppm: 8.354 (d, J = 9.6 Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 7.865 (t, J = 6.4Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 7.564 (t, J = 7.8 Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 7.448 (d, J = 7.6 Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 7.347 (d, J = 10.8 Hz, 2H,Ar-H); ¹³CNMR(100 MHz,CDCl₃)δppm :164.99, 152.45, 142.20, 137.06, 128.12,128.05, 126.77, 125.21, 124.11, 120.36, 110.66; LCMS:(m/z): 230.47(M+1). Molecular formulae: C₁₃H₈ClNO.

2.1.7.2-(4-(Bromo phenyl) benzoxazole (3f)

Pale red solid, Yield-88%, M.P-192-194⁰C, ¹HNMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ ppm : 8.248 (d, J = 9.0 Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 7.824 (t, J = 6.8Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 7.664 (t, J = 7.6 Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 7.462 (d, J = 8.0 Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 7.247 (d, J = 8.8 Hz, 2H, Ar-H); ¹³CNMR(100 MHz,CDCl₃)δppm :168.15, 154.48, 143.20, 138.16, 129.12, 128.55, 127.07, 125.74, 123.68, 121.36, 112.66; LCMS:(m/z): 270.47(M+1) Molecular formulae: C₁₃H₈BrNO

2.1.7.2-(4-(Nitro phenyl) benzoxazole (3g)

Yellow solid, Yield-82%, M.P-213-215⁰C, ¹HNMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ ppm : 8.354 (d, J = 6.8 Hz, 2H, Ar), 7.857 (t, J = 7.0Hz, 1H, Ar), 7.674 (t, J = 7.2 Hz, 1H, Ar), 7.562 (d, J = 8.4 Hz, 2H, Ar), 7.287 (d, J = 8.4 Hz, 2H, Ar); ¹³CNMR(100 MHz,CDCl₃)δppm : 184.25, 156.48, 144.20, 139.16, 128.82, 128.14, 127.88, 126.67, 124.74, 122.36, 113.75; LCMS:(m/z): 240.28(M+H) Molecular formulae: C₁₃H₈N₂O₃

2.1.8.2-(Thiophen-3-yl) benzoxazole (3h)

Milky white solid, Yield-86%, M.P-178-180⁰C, ¹HNMR(400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ ppm : 8.354 (d, J = 6.8 Hz, 1H), 7.854 (d, J = 4.5Hz,1H), 7.652 (t, J = 7.6Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 7.454 (t, J = 7.8 Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 7.404 (s, 1H, Ar-H), 7.394-7.315(m, 2H, Ar-H); ¹³CNMR(100 MHz,CDCl₃) δ ppm: 164.07, 152.88, 142.65,129.54, 128.52, 127.15, 126.30, 125.49, 122.43, 119.51, 111.04; LCMS:(m/z): 202.65 (M+H). Molecular formulae: C₁₁H₇NOS

2.1.9.2-(Pyridine-2-yl) benzoxazole (3i)

Milky white solid, Yield-84%, M.P-174-176⁰C, ¹HNMR(400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ ppm; 8.524(d, J = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 8.112 (d, J = 9.6 Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 7.774 (t, J = 6.4 Hz,1H, Ar-H), 7.487 (t, J = 8.0 Hz, 1H, Ar-H), 7.415-7.326 (m, 2H); ¹³CNMR(100 MHz,CDCl₃) δ ppm : 163.88, 151.78, 146.78, 141.57, 136.81, 128.85, 127.29,121.34, 119.06, 111.54; LCMS:(m/z): 197

.56(M+1). Molecular formulae: C₁₂H₈N₂O

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

2-aminophenol and substituted aromatic aldehydes were selected as the model reaction to evaluate catalytic activity of NiSO₄ at ambient temperature. To recognize the required for this condensation reaction.

(3a-3h)

R = H, 4-OH, 4-OCH₃, 4-Br, 4-CF₃, 4-Cl, thiophene, Pyridine

(Scheme-1)

Table 1: Effectiveness of the catalyst for synthesis of compound (3f).

S.NO	Catalyst	Time(min)	Yield (%)
1	KI	180	71
2	CuI ₂	180	92
3	I ₂	180	90

The effectiveness of the catalyst for the preparation of the desired compounds and also the effective yield developed and time factor also significant role play of the catalyst. There are various catalysts applied on this model of the reaction such as KI, CuI₂ and I₂. The excellent results observed for use of the CuI₂.

Table 2: Optimization of amount catalyst for synthesis of compound (3f).

S.NO	Loaded Catalyst	Time(min)	Yield (%)
1	No catalyst	180	Rare
2	2mole	180	59
3	4mole	180	92
4	5mole	180	92

We examined that the model reaction could not proceed in the absence of catalyst after 24 hrs and when using a catalytic amount of 4 mol% CuI₂, the reaction scaffold required compounds with 92% yield in 1.5 h in EtOH, and further decreasing the catalyst loading up to 5 mol% led

to lower yield of 55% in 1.5 h. In the presence of 20 mol% catalyst the reaction affords the corresponding synthesis of benzoxazole in 98% yield within 1.5 h, and CuI₂ also gives 98% yield in 1.5 h.

Table 3: Optimization of solvent for synthesis of compound (3f).

S.NO	Solvent	Time(min)	Yield (%)
1	CH ₃ CN	180	72
2	DMF	180	57
3	EtOH	180	94
4	DCM	280	61

The solvents examined were dichloromethane, acetonitrile and ethanol, among which ethanol is shown to be the good. Accordingly, 20 mol% CuI₂ catalysts loading in EtOH is considered optimal for the synthesis of benzoxazole. To word, we prepared a range of benzoxazole under the optimized conditions. 2-Aminophenol, different aldehydes were coupled with under these reaction conditions. The reactions are clean and highly selective affording exclusively benzoxazole in high yields in a short reaction time.

3.2. ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY OF COMPOUNDS

The micro broth dilution method was used to assess the titled derivatives' *invitro* antibacterial and antifungal properties such Gr- (-) (E. coli and P. aeruginosa) and Gr- (+) (B. subtilis and S. aureus) microorganisms were used to test the invitro antibacterial activity. The microorganisms Aspergillums Niger and C. albicans were used to test the antifungal activity in vitro. For this investigation, streptomycin was used as the standard drug to screen for bacteria. A Ketonazole screening for antifungals was conducted. The standard strains used to screen for antibacterial and antifungal activity were supplied by the Culture Collection and Geneank (MTCC), which is situated in Chandigarh, India. Mueller Hinton Broth was used to feed the bacteria, and Sabouraud dextrose Broth was used to grow the fungi. By comparing the turbidity, the inoculum size for the test strain was optimized to 10⁸ CFU/mL. Primary and secondary evaluations of the results were documented. The compounds under investigation and standard medications were diluted twice in succession to create a stock solution (2000 µg/mL).

Table 4: Screening of antimicrobial activity of titled derivatives (3a-3h).

Entry	Antibacterial strains			
	B. subtilis	S. aureus	P. aeruginosa	E. coli
3a	05	07	08	06
3b	18	17	17	12
3c	16	18	20	17
3d	21	21	20	20
3e	22	20	18	18
3f	21	19	19	18
3g	11	12	13	12
3h	10	16	15	14
Streptomycin	25	25	25	25
Ketozazole	-	-	-	-
DMSO				

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we have developed a novel and highly efficient method for the synthesis of benzoxazole by treatment of 2-aminophenol and substituted aryl aldehyde in the presence of CuI_2 as an effective transition metal halide. The significant advantages of this methodology are moderate to good yields, short reaction times, a simple workup procedure, and easy preparation and handling of the catalyst. This methodology may find widespread uses in organic synthesis for preparation of the benzoxazole.

5. AKOWNLDEMENT

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